

Synthesis, characterization and biological assay of vanillin and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone based terpolymer resin and its chelates with transition and inner transition metal ions

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Abstract : Polymer metal complexes of three transition and two rare earth elements were prepared by condensation polymerization technique using *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, vanillin and formaldehyde. As-synthesized terpolymer and its metal complexes were subjected to spectral characterization by UV-Visible, FTIR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR. The molecular weight of terpolymer was determined by gel permeation chromatography. The thermal stability of the terpolymer and metal complexes were determined by TGA and DSC techniques. *In vitro* biological tests were performed for both; the ligand and its polymer metal complexes against certain pathogenic bacteria such as *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, *S. pyogenes* and fungi such as *C. albicans*, *A. niger* and *A. clavatus*.

Keywords : Terpolymer, metal complexes, thermogravimetric analysis, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

The functional group containing polymers find applications in fields like biochemistry, inorganic chemistry and pharmaceutical sciences¹. The increase in ailments by pathogenic microorganisms has led to the development of materials for example, metal complexes derived from various novel ligands possessing antimicrobial activity². Ahamed and Burkanudeen³ prepared a terpolymer ligand from 2-amino-6-nitro-benzothiazole, thiosemicarbazide and formaldehyde followed by synthesis of its metal complexes. The synthesized compounds were screened for antimicrobial activity. Zinc complexes showed excellent antibacterial activity.

Nishat *et al.*⁴ prepared urea-formaldehyde resin and its metal complexes with Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}. The complexes were found to possess good thermal stability and reasonably good antibacterial activity as compared to standard drugs. Ahamad *et al.*⁵ synthesized and characterized a new class of metal chelated polyureas by the reaction of toluene

2,4-diisocyanate (TDI) with chelated Schiff base diamines using Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal ions. All the polymers showed good antibacterial activity. Patel *et al.*⁶ synthesized the polymeric ligand (resin) from 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone with 1,3-propane diol in the presence of polyphosphoric acid as a catalyst. Metal polymer complexes using lanthanides(III) were prepared. It was found that the resin has good binding capacity for the lanthanides and good antimicrobial activity compared to free polymeric ligand. Chetana *et al.*⁷ synthesized a novel Schiff base ligand, 4-chloro-2-(pyridine-3-yliminomethyl) phenol and its transition metal complexes using Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}. The complexes were screened for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activity using various strains of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. It was found that the Schiff base ligand showed higher antibacterial activity than the ligand coordinated to either of the metal ions. Alshehri *et al.*⁸ synthesized a terpolymer from salicylaldehyde, phenylthiourea and glutaraldehyde. The polarity of the metal ion in com-

plexes was reduced, which might contribute to its superior antimicrobial property.

Khan *et al.*⁹ synthesized a novel tetradentate salicylic acid-formaldehyde terpolymer ligand containing piperazine moiety by condensation polymerization. It was subjected to chelation with metal ions like Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} . It was reported that antibacterial and antifungal activity was increased on chelation. Azarudeen *et al.*¹⁰ synthesized a chelating terpolymer resin from anthranilic acid, 2-amino pyridine and formaldehyde. The resin was used to remove the heavy metal ions present in the solutions. Azarudeen *et al.*¹¹ reported growth of few bacteria and their inhibitions in presence of synthesized terpolymer metal complexes of transition metal ions using a terpolymer ligand derived from anthranilic acid-phenyl hydrazine-formaldehyde. Salih¹² synthesized metal complexes of polycyclicacetal derived from polyvinyl alcohol and erythro-ascorbic acid derivative and found good antimicrobial activities.

In this paper, synthesis of a novel terpolymer ligand using *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, vanillin and formaldehyde has been reported. Metal complexes of Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , La^{III} and Nd^{III} were prepared with synthesized terpolymer as ligand. The ligand and complexes were characterized by spectral and thermal methods. The antimicrobial properties of ligand and its polymer metal complexes were screened against four bacterial strains and three fungal strains.

Experimental

Materials :

o-Hydroxyacetophenone (Acros Organics), glacial acetic acid (Rankem), vanillin (Hi-media), formaldehyde (Rankem 37–41%), cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate $Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Merck), zinc(II) nitrate hexahydrate $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Merck), cupric nitrate $Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ (Fischer Scientific), lanthanum(III) nitrate hexahydrate $La(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Alfa Aesar) and neodymium(III) nitrate hexahydrate $Nd(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Alfa Aesar) were used in present investigations. Solvents such as acetone (Merck), dimethylformamide (Sd fine chem. Ltd.) and ethanol were purified by standard procedures before use. All other chemicals were used as received.

Synthesis of terpolymer :

The terpolymer ligand was synthesized by solution condensation polymerization technique in acidic medium as shown in Scheme 1. *Ortho*-hydroxyacetophenone (*o*-HAP) (0.2 mol) was taken in a round bottom flask and then vanillin(v) (0.2 mol) dissolved in 15 mL of glacial acetic acid was slowly added into it. It was followed by addition of formaldehyde (F) (10 mL) dropwise into the reaction mixture. It was refluxed at 100–120 °C for about 10–12 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC). After the reaction time was over, it was allowed to cool. A black coloured terpolymer resin obtained was separated and washed several times with warm water and ethanol to remove the unreacted monomers. The resin was air dried and powdered well.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of terpolymer ligand.

Synthesis of metal complexes :

The polymer metal complexes were prepared by using equimolar ratio (1 : 1) of terpolymer ligand and metal salts. The *o*-HAP-VF-Co, *o*-HAP-VF-Zn, *o*-HAP-VF-Cu, *o*-HAP-VF-Nd and *o*-HAP-VF-La terpolymer metal complexes were prepared by the following general procedure :

The terpolymer ligand (0.05 mol) was dissolved in acetone and the metal nitrates (0.05 mol) of Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cu^{II} , Nd^{III} and La^{III} were dissolved in acetone separately and both the solutions were filtered off. The resultant solutions were mixed together with constant stirring and refluxed for 6–8 h at 50–60 °C. The metal complexes obtained were separated and washed with alcohol. Then, these metal complexes were air dried. The reaction scheme for the preparation of the polychelates is shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of metal complexes of *o*-HAP-VF.

Spectral analysis :

The UV-Visible (UV-Vis) spectra of terpolymer and its metal complexes were recorded in dimethylformamide (DMF) as solvent. For this purpose, a UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer-Lambda 750 from

Perkin-Elmer, USA was used in the range of 200–1100 nm. A Perkin-Elmer Spectrum-RX-FTIR spectrophotometer was used to obtain the IR spectra between 4000 to 250 cm^{-1} . The samples were prepared in pellet form using spectroscopic grade KBr. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded using $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ as a solvent in Cryo-magnet Spectrometer model Avance-II (Bruker) 400 MHz spectrometer (USA).

Thermal analysis :

Thermal behavior (Thermogravimetric analysis-TGA) of all the synthesized polymeric compounds was determined on Thermal analyzer, model Pyris-1 TGA (Perkin-Elmer) in the range from room temperature to 1000 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. Phase transitions were investigated over the range of 50–300 °C in nitrogen atmosphere using a Perkin-Elmer Diamond differential scanning calorimetry (DSC).

GPC :

The average molecular weight and its polydispersity index were determined by Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC) analysis. It was performed with a set up consisting of a Perkin-Elmer 200 pumps and 2 ultra Styragel columns (10^4 , 500 Å) with THF as the eluent at a flow rate of 1 mL/min equipped with Waters differential refractometer and calibrated with a standard linear.

Antimicrobial activity :

Antimicrobial activity was performed by using micro-broth dilution method. Serial dilutions were prepared for primary and secondary screening ranging from 50 to 1000 ppm and the minimum inhibitory concentration that inhibits the growth of microorganisms was determined. The standard drugs used for comparing antibacterial activity are Gentamycin, Ampicillin, Chloramphenicol, Ciprofloxacin and Norfloxacin and for antifungal activity two standard drugs Nystatin and Griseofulvin were used.

Results and discussion

UV-Visible spectra :

The UV-Visible absorption spectrum of *o*-HAP-VF terpolymer ligand showed two characteristic bands in the region around 250 nm and 325 nm. The band

at 250 nm indicates the presence of a carbonyl (>C=O) group containing a carbon oxygen double bond conjugated with an aromatic nucleus due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition whereas the band at 325 nm may be due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ electronic transition. Both these bands are shifted to longer wavelength due to presence of auxochrome phenolic -OH group.

The electronic spectral data of terpolymer metal complexes are given in Supplementary Table 1. *o*-HAP-VF-Zn and *o*-HAP-VF-La complexes did not show electronic transitions due to their diamagnetic nature. The *o*-HAP-VF -Cu complex shows two types of transitions 16129 cm^{-1} and 26315 cm^{-1} which are assigned to ${}^2E \rightarrow {}^2T_2$ transition and a charge transfer transition in an octahedral environment with magnetic moment of 1.73 B.M. The *o*-HAP-VF -Co complex shows three electronic transitions 12345 cm^{-1} , 14992

cm^{-1} and 20833 cm^{-1} , which are assigned to ${}^4T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_2(F)$, ${}^4T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_2(F)$ and ${}^4T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transitions in an octahedral environment with magnetic moment of 3.46 B.M. The *o*-HAP-VF-Nd complex exhibits transitions at 28985 cm^{-1} , 22471 cm^{-1} and 16638 cm^{-1} , which are assigned to ${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4G_{9/2}$, ${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4G_{5/2}$ and ${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4F_{9/2}$ transitions, respectively in an octahedral environment with magnetic moment of 4.47 B.M. The geometry of the polymer metal complexes were proposed based on the data observed.

FTIR spectra :

The FTIR spectral data of the terpolymer ligand and its metal complexes are presented in Supplementary Table 2. The FTIR spectra of *o*-HAP-VF terpolymer shows a strong band at 3399 cm^{-1} , which is assigned to the -OH stretching frequency of phenolic group. This band gets broader in the polymer metal

Table 1. MIC values for *o*-HAP-VF and its metal complexes

Sr. No.	Synthesized compounds	Minimum inhibition concentration ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)			
		<i>E. coli</i> (MTCC 443)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> (MTCC 441)	<i>S. aureus</i> (MTCC 96)	<i>S. pyogenes</i> (MTCC 442)
1.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF	200	500	100	100
2.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF-Cu	100	62.5	25	50
3.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF-Co	12.5	100	100	50
4.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF-Zn	125	200	100	100
5.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF-La	25	50	100	25
6.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF-Nd	25	12.5	62.5	50
	Gentamycin	0.05	1	0.25	0.5
	Ampicillin	100	-	250	100
	Chloramphenicol	50	50	50	50
	Ciprofloxacin	25	25	50	50
	Norfloxacin	10	10	10	10

Table 2. MIC values for *o*-HAP-VF and its metal complexes

Sr. No.	Synthesized compounds	Minimum inhibition concentration ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)		
		<i>C. albicans</i> (MTCC 227)	<i>A. niger</i> (MTCC 282)	<i>A. clavatus</i> (MTCC 1323)
1.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF	100	250	250
2.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF-Cu	100	200	100
3.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF-Co	500	100	250
4.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF-Zn	100	250	100
5.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF-La	250	100	200
6.	<i>o</i> -HAP-VF-Nd	250	50	100
	Nystatin	100	100	100
	Greseofulvin	500	100	100

complexes; may be due to the bonding of -OH group to the metal ion. The broad band around 3450 cm^{-1} for the complexes suggests the existence of coordinated water in all the complexes. The -CH₂-linkage in terpolymer is assigned to a band at 2870 cm^{-1} . The band at 1455 cm^{-1} may be due to the aromatic -C=C stretching. A strong band at 1297 cm^{-1} is assigned to -C-O stretching. The metal oxygen bonding is confirmed by the bands at $633\text{--}635\text{ cm}^{-1}$ while band at $800\text{--}900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ confirms the presence of substitution in benzene ring.

NMR spectra :

The aromatic protons show multiplet between δ 6–7 ppm. The singlet at δ 9.7 ppm is assigned to

-CHO group and signals appearing at δ 5.0 ppm are due to proton of -OH group. The signal at δ 2.58 ppm is due to methyl protons of -COCH₃ group. The signal of bridge methylene group of *o*-HAP-VF ligand appears at δ 3.9 ppm. A singlet at δ 3.73 is assigned to methyl protons of -OCH₃ group. The results of ¹H NMR spectra reveal that the vanillin is attached to *o*-hydroxyacetophenone moiety via methylene group of formaldehyde. The spectral data are presented in Supplementary Fig. 1.

The signal for the proton of -OH group disappeared in the ¹H NMR spectra of metal complexes, which reveals the participation of -OH protons to the metal centre in the formation of -C-O-M-. The pro-

Fig. 1. Gel permeation chromatograph of *o*-HAP-VF terpolymer.

tons of -CHO group were shifted downfield at δ 10.4 ppm and a significant shifting in all the peaks were observed, which confirmed the formation of polymer-metal complexes. The ^1H NMR spectrum of *o*-HAP-VF-Cu metal complex is shown in Supplementary Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. TGA of *o*-HAP-VF terpolymer and its metal complexes.

^{13}C NMR spectra :

The spectrum of the terpolymer shows the peaks at 155.1, 124.7, 127.7, 135.7, 150.3 and 122.9 ppm for six carbons of aromatic ring. The peak at 26.9 corresponds to bridge methylene group of terpolymer. A sharp peak at 196.5 and 190.0 corresponds to carbonyl group of -COCH₃ and -CHO, respectively.

The spectra of metal complexes showed similar peaks for aromatic ring carbon atoms as observed for terpolymer ligand. The shifting of peaks of methylene carbon of terpolymer from 26.9 to 30.0 ppm in complexes revealed that coordination has taken place between oxygen atoms of the ligand and metal ion.

Molecular weight measurement :

The number and weight average molecular weights (\bar{M}_n and \bar{M}_w) were found to be 261.3 and 4736.7, respectively. The average molecular weight (\bar{M}_z) of the terpolymer was found to be 30002. The polydispersity index (\bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n) for the terpolymer was found to be 18.127, which clearly indicate the broad molecular weight distribution in the polymer. The single peak in Fig. 1 of gel permeation chromatogram clearly shows that complete polymerization of terpolymer ligand has taken place.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) :

The thermal stability of synthesized moieties was examined by their thermogravimetric analysis. The recorded thermograms are shown in Fig. 2 and the weight percentage left at various temperatures are given in Supplementary Table 3. From the thermogram of *o*-HAP-VF terpolymer, three stages of degradation (100–300, 300–500 and 500–700 °C) have been observed. Initial loss upto 150 °C was attributed due to the less loosely bonded water. The weight loss obtained in the range of 150–200 °C might be due to metal coordinated water molecules. The rate of decomposition for the entire coordination polymers is initially low upto 200 °C, which gradually increases in the range of 300–700 °C, at which about 55–70% loss in weight was observed; may be due to the loss of side groups attached to the terpolymer ligand. The thermal analysis data revealed that the metal complexes show comparatively good thermal stability compared to terpolymer.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) :

The samples were heated at a rate of 10 °C/min from 50 to 300 °C in the atmosphere of nitrogen. The plots reflected that DSC heat flow as a function of sample temperature and endothermic response (heat is absorbed during melting of samples) is oriented towards bottom of graph. The enthalpy changes involved during melting of samples, onset temperatures and peak temperatures (melting temperatures) are reported in Supplementary Table 4. The onset temperature for *o*-HAP-VF terpolymer is 75.74 °C which melts at 92.37 °C with total heat of melting of 12.25 J/g. The terpolymer metal complexes of Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, La^{III} and Nd^{III} melts at 85.32, 89.36, 77.32, 90.54 and 88.36 °C with total heat of melting of 34.04 J/g, 27.35 J/g, 15.39 J/g, 37.63 J/g and 28.34 J/g, respectively (Supplementary Fig. 3). The greater enthalpy of fusion for all the complexes as compared to terpolymer ligand showed their greater stability. It is also expected that enthalpy changes may be almost the same for the complexes, which have very similar compositions; however the value of enthalpy of fusion is highest for *o*-HAP-VF-La complex.

Antimicrobial screening :

Antibacterial activity of o-HAP-VF and its metal complexes :

Antibacterial activities of synthesized terpolymer and its metal complexes are reported in Table 1 and shown graphically in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Antibacterial activity of terpolymer and its metal complexes.

The results of antibacterial assay revealed that compound **3** showed excellent activity (MIC = 12.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) against *E. coli* in comparison with standard drugs Ampicillin, Chloramphenicol and Ciprofloxacin. The compounds **4** and **6** were reported to show excellent activity for *E. coli* in comparison with Ampicillin and Chloramphenicol whereas the same compounds show equipotent activity with standard Ciprofloxacin. Compound **3** showed equipotent activity as compared to Ampicillin while compound **5** was found to be active at little higher MIC value as compared to Ampicillin. Compound **6** was found to possess excellent activity (MIC = 12.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) for *P. aeruginosa*, when compared with standard drugs Chloramphenicol and Ciprofloxacin. The compound **5** was found to show equal activity for *P. aeruginosa* as compared to Chloramphenicol. The compound **2** and **6** showed excellent activity against *S. aureus* as compared to standard drugs Ampicillin, Chloramphenicol and Ciprofloxacin. The compounds **1** and **3-5** (MIC = 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) were found to exhibit excellent activity for *S. aureus* as compared to standard drug Ampicillin. The compound **4** showed excellent activity against *S. pyogenes* as compared to standard drug Ampicillin,

Chloramphenicol and Ciprofloxacin. The compounds **2**, **3** and **6** showed excellent activity against *S. pyogenes* as compared to standard drug Ampicillin and equipotent activity compared to Chloramphenicol and Ciprofloxacin.

Antifungal activity of o-HAP-VF and its metal complexes :

Antifungal activities of synthesized terpolymer and its metal complexes are reported in Table 2 and shown graphically in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Antifungal activity of terpolymer and its metal complexes.

The results of antifungal assay revealed that the compounds **1-2** and **4-6** showed good activity and compound **3** showed equipotent activity against *C. albicans* as compared to standard drug Griseofulvin while compounds **1-2** and **5** showed equipotent activity against the standard drug Nystatin. The compound **6** showed excellent activity and compound **3-4** showed equipotent activity for *A. niger* against both the standard drugs Nystatin and Griseofulvin. The compounds **2**, **5** and **6** were found to be equally active for *A. clavatus* against the standard drugs Nystatin and Griseofulvin.

In general, the polychelates showed higher activity as compared to the ligand. This may be attributed to the delocalization of π -electron over the whole chelate ring. The lanthanides have preference to strongly bind with chelating species containing more electronegative atoms like oxygen and nitrogen atoms. Greater antimicrobial activity of lanthanum and neodymium complexes may be attributed to the higher charge

density (La^{3+} and Nd^{3+}) and their small size as compared to transition metal ions. Due to this reason, orbitals containing lone pair on oxygen atom of the ligand are highly polarized imparting greater covalent character to O-M bond, more than expected. As a result, lipophilic character of complexes is greatly enhanced. Increased lipophilicities allow the penetration of complexes through the cell of pathogenic microbes making them deactivated by interacting with their active enzymes.

Conclusion

Terpolymer ligand containing vanillin, *ortho*-hydroxyacetophenone and formaldehyde was successfully synthesized by solution condensation polymerization technique keeping the medium acidic. The metal complexes of Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , La^{II} and Nd^{III} ions with this terpolymer ligand were successfully prepared. The spectral characterization revealed octahedral geometry of metal complexes. The thermal data showed that the metal complexes possess good thermal stability as compared to ligand alone. The antibacterial studies revealed that some of the metal complexes have better antimicrobial activity. The *o*-HAP-VF-Co complex shows highest antibacterial activity.

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